

The determinants of data use practice for instructional practice in higher education

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Summary

1. The study aims to predict the influence of various teacher characteristics on the degree of data use for instructional purposes.
2. Data use potentially improves instructional practices and student outcomes.
3. Key factors include pedagogical knowledge, data literacy, content knowledge, knowledge of English for teaching, and attitudes toward data.
4. Pedagogical knowledge is the most potent predictor of the frequency of instructional data use practices.

1. Introduction

In the increasing need for data-driven teaching, using data to enhance instructional practices has emerged as a vital approach to improving instructional practices and student outcomes (Mandinach & Schilkamp, 2021). Data-driven teaching is crucial for creating targeted, effective learning environments that cater to the diverse needs of students. By leveraging data, educators can move beyond

intuition or tradition and instead base their instructional decisions on concrete evidence. This approach enables teachers to identify learning gaps, track student progress, and tailor their teaching methods to address specific challenges. Moreover, it encourages a culture of continuous improvement, where data is not only used to evaluate past performance but also to guide future instruction. The integration of data into teaching practices leads to more personalized and adaptive learning experiences, ultimately

resulting in better student outcomes and more equitable education systems.

This policy brief highlights the impact of teacher characteristics on data use for instructional purposes in higher education, focusing on a study conducted in a developing country (Ansyari, Groot & De Witte, 2024). We empirically determine which characteristics most significantly influence data use practices.

The study conducted in Indonesia offers valuable insights that extend beyond its local context, making it relevant for Europe and applicable to other subjects as well. First, the core principles of data-driven teaching—enhancing instructional practices and student outcomes—are universal. As European educational systems increasingly prioritize evidence-based approaches, the findings from this study can inform strategies for improving teaching across disciplines. Additionally, language education is present in about all education systems. The study's focus on teacher characteristics, such as pedagogical knowledge and data literacy, provides transferable lessons for improving professional development and instructional effectiveness in various educational settings.

2. Methodology

The methodology employed a decision tree analysis to identify significant predictors of data use in teaching utilizing a national survey of 204 English teachers across 58 Indonesian Islamic higher education institutions. The survey assessed various teacher attributes, including data literacy, pedagogical and content knowledge, English proficiency, and attitudes toward data. The decision tree approach segmented data into homogenous groups, revealing correlations between

teacher characteristics and effective data use. These results will inform policy recommendations to strengthen teacher development and optimize data use in educational practices.

3. Results

The study's analysis revealed several significant findings regarding the factors that influence instructional data use among English teachers (See Figure 1). The decision tree analysis indicated that pedagogical knowledge emerged as the strongest predictor of the frequent use of data in teaching. Teachers who possess a solid foundation in pedagogical knowledge are significantly more likely to engage more deeply with data and apply it to enhance their instructional practices.

In addition to pedagogical knowledge, data literacy and content knowledge were also identified as critical factors of the frequent use of data. Teachers with higher levels of data literacy demonstrated greater use of data to inform their instructional practices. Conversely, general English proficiency was not found to be a significant predictor of data use in this context. This indicates that language skills alone do not translate into frequent use of data to improve teaching practices and student learning outcomes.

Moreover, teachers' attitudes toward data played an essential role in their willingness to utilize data in their instruction. Those who viewed data as a valuable tool for addressing student needs were more likely to incorporate data-driven approaches in their teaching.

4. Policy Recommendations

The findings offer valuable insights for policymakers to enhance teacher professionalism and improve instructional methods, ultimately benefiting student learning outcomes. In light of the study's findings, policymakers need to enhance the professional development of educators. It is essential to develop programs that focus on improving teachers' **data use for pedagogical ability**. These programs should incorporate active learning strategies that address real classroom challenges. By using various types of data—including outcome, process, and context data—teachers will be empowered to make informed decisions that enhance student learning outcomes.

Alternatively, designing **professional development programs** that utilize a **blended learning approach**—combining synchronous (real-time) and asynchronous (self-paced) formats—will create flexible and accessible learning options for educators. This flexibility accommodates busy schedules and diverse learning styles, as teachers can engage in meaningful reflection and apply new skills at their own pace while still benefiting from real-time interactions.

In addition, a **Professional Learning Community (PLC)** can provide a great environment and ongoing support for teachers as they implement data-driven practices. These collaborative environments will encourage teachers to engage in discussions about data insights, best practices, and the challenges they face, fostering a supportive culture of continuous improvement within the educational setting.

Finally, advocating for **strong policy support** and adequate **resource allocation** is essential for sustaining professional development

efforts aimed at improving data use in education. This includes securing dedicated funding, administrative backing, and legal endorsements that encourage a culture of data-driven decision-making.

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Figure 1. Decision Tree (Source/s: Figure created by authors)

NOTE: The tree starts with pedagogical knowledge as the root node shown at the top, representing the most influential attribute in predicting the degrees of instructional data use practice as the leaves (the grey circles). This root node is followed by data literacy and content knowledge (branches) that indicate the second influential attribute. Content knowledge, attitudes and English-for-teaching become the third influential attribute.

Further Information:

Ansyari, M.F., Groot, W. and De Witte, K. (2024). The determinants of data use practice for instructional practice in higher education. *Journal of Professional Capital and Community*. <https://www.emerald.com/insight/content/doi/10.1108/JPCC-07-2024-0106/full/html>

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